

energy of activation ΔF and entropy of activation ΔS have been computed at 35° and recorded in Table 2. For this calculation our own viscosity data for dioxane-water mixtures have been used. It is observed that the energy and entropy of activation of viscous flow in case of NaCl is greater than that of the solvent whereas it is less in case of NaBr and NaNO₃. The large energy and entropy of activation are attributed to the excess of energy necessary to break the hydrogen bonds in solutions, i.e., for NaCl. In case of bromide and nitrate structure is broken down at all solvent compositions. From Table 2, it is seen that the ion-solvent interaction is of the order Br⁻ > NO₃⁻ > Cl⁻ and is in agreement with that of Kay⁷, who distinguished between the structure breaking and structure making ions by plotting $\Delta(\lambda^0\eta_r)/\Delta T$ vs $\Delta B \frac{1}{2}\Delta T$.

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Optical Resolution of ($\pm$) α -(*o*, *m*-carboxyphenylamino)-Arylacetonitriles

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α -Aminonitriles being the most important intermediates for the synthesis of amino acids, we have prepared¹⁻⁴ a number of them of type ($\pm$) R-C₆H₄-CH(CN)-NH-R', where R = -OH or -OCH₃, R' = *o*- or *m*-carboxyphenyl groups. We reported here the optical resolution of α -(*o* or *m*-carboxyphenylamino)-*m* or *p*-hydroxyphenyl or

p-methoxyphenyl acetonitrile into their enantiomers through their brucine salts. The optical rotations measured in different solvents showed that the introduction of hydroxy group in α -(*m*-carboxyphenylamino)-phenylacetonitrile decreases the absolute value of optical rotation while that of methoxy group in α -(*o*-carboxyphenylamino) phenylacetonitrile increases the optical activity.

Experimental

Resolution of ($\pm$) α -(*o*-carboxyphenylamino)-*p*-methoxyphenylacetonitrile

A clear solution of ($\pm$) α -(*o*-Carboxyphenylamino)-*p*-methoxyphenylacetonitrile² (5.64 g) and (-)-brucine (7.29 g) in hot acetone (70 ml) on cooling for 72 hrs. deposited a crystalline salt, *crop A* (6.5 g), m.p. 130-32°. On two further crystallisations from a mixture of acetone and chloroform, *crop A* yielded *crop C* (1 g), m.p. 138°. The latter on decomposition yielded the optically pure (+)-nitrile, m.p. 150-51°, [α]_D+70°. Further crystallisations did not increase the optical rotation.

The mother liquor was concentrated to get *crop A'* (6.5 g) m.p. 118-20°, part of which was decomposed to (-)-nitrile [α]_D-23° (C=1.5). On two further crystallisation from a mixture of acetone and chloroform it gave *crop C'* (1 g) m.p. 134° which on decomposition gave (-)-nitrile, m.p. 148° [α]_D-40°. The rotation did not increase on further crystallisation.

Resolution of ($\pm$)- α -(*m*-Carboxyphenylamino)-*m*-hydroxyphenylacetonitrile :

A clear solution of ($\pm$)- α -(*m*-carboxyphenylamino)-*m*-hydroxyphenylacetonitrile⁴ (10.72 g) and (-)-brucine (15.58 g) in hot acetone (200 ml.) was subjected to fractional crystallisations as above. The fully active (+)-nitrile, m.p. 155°, [α]_D+20° and (-)-nitrile, m.p. 154-55°, [α]_D-20° were obtained.

Resolution of ($\pm$)- α -(*m*-Carboxyphenylamino)-*p*-hydroxyphenylacetonitrile :

(-)-Brucine (11.8 g) was added to ($\pm$)- α -(*m*-carboxyphenylamino)-*p*-hydroxyphenylacetonitrile⁴

TABLE-1

OPTICAL ROTATIONS OF α -AMINONITRILES* OF THE TYPE (+) AND (-) R-C₆H₄-CH(CN)-NH-R' IN DIFFERENT SOLVENTS†

Solvent	R= <i>p</i> -methoxy R'= <i>o</i> -carboxyphenyl		R= <i>m</i> -hydroxy R'= <i>m</i> -carboxyphenyl		R= <i>p</i> -hydroxy R'= <i>m</i> -carboxyphenyl							
	(+) isomer	(-) isomer	(+) isomer	(-) isomer	(+) isomer	(-) isomer						
	conc [α] _D	conc [α] _D	conc [α] _D	conc [α] _D	conc [α] _D	conc [α] _D						
Acetone	1.0	+70.0	0.5	-40.0	0.7	+20.0	0.8	-20.0	1.0	+15.0	1.1	-18.0
Ethanol	1.0	+68.0	0.7	-38.0	1.0	+18.0	0.7	-15.0	1.1	+12.0	1.2	-15.0
Methanol	0.7	+60.0	0.8	-35.0	1.2	+15.0	1.0	-12.0	1.2	+10.0	1.0	-15.0
Dioxane	0.6	+58.0	1.0	-38.0	1.1	+12.0	1.1	-12.0	1.2	+10.0	1.3	-12.0
Ethylacetate	0.8	+70.0	1.1	-40.0	1.0	+20.0	1.2	-18.0	1.1	+15.0	1.2	-17.0

* All the isomers gave correct N analysis.

† All the optical rotations were measured at 23°. (l=1)

(8.05 g) in hot acetone (150 ml). The clear solution of brucine salt on two fractional crystallisations gave (-)-nitrile, m.p. 178°, $[\alpha]_D - 18^\circ$ (c=1.2) and (+)-nitrile, m.p. 176° $[\alpha]_D + 15^\circ$.

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Synthesis of Some 4-Hydroxybromoquinoline-3-Carboxylic Acids

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IN continuation of our previous work^{1,2} attempts were made to apply the acetic anhydride-sulphuric acid method to cyclise acrylates prepared by condensing ethyl ethoxymethylene-malonate or cyanoacetate with 5-bromo-*o*-toluidine, 3-bromo-*p*-toluidine, 4:6-dibromo-*m*-toluidine, 4-bromo-*o*-anisidine and 4-bromo-*o*-phenetidine. Since the yields of the cyclised products obtained with this method were poor due to the decomposition of the acrylates resulting in the formation of bromoacetyl anilides, the acrylates were cyclised by the thermal method of Price and Roberts³.

TABLE-1

ARYLAMINOACRYLATES $R_1 = -COOC_2H_5$ OR $-CN$

	R_2	R_3	R_4	R_1	Yield %	m.p.s.	R_1'	Yield %	m.p.s
1.	H	Br	CH_3	$-COOC_2H_5$	77	106°	$-CN$	76	195°
2.	H	CH_3	Br	"	83	86	"	96	192
3.	CH_3	Br	Br	"	75	Sticky	"	51	225
4.	Br	H	OCH_3	"	34	118	"	31	140
5.	Br	H	OC_2H_5	"	93	105	"	37	173

TABLE-2

4-HYDROXYQUINOLINES

	R_2	R_3	R_4	(a) R_1	Yield %	m.p.s	(b) R_1	Yield %	m.p.s.	R_1	Yield: % a b	m.p.s.
1.	H	Br	CH_3	$-COOC_2H_5$	77	310	$-CN$	94	330° dec.	$-COOH$	78 41	301° dec.
2.	H	CH_3	Br	"	88	262	"	61	360	"	68 75	360
3.	CH_3	Br	Br	"	27	305	"	84	300 dec.	"	72 33	277
4.	Br	H	OCH_3	"	52	295	"	28	200	"	87 34	290
5.	Br	H	OC_2H_5	"	Sticky		"	19	291 dec.	"	19.5 56	281